

ТЕОРІЯ І МЕТОДИКА ПРОФЕСІЙНОЇ ОСВІТИ

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Моделі професійного розвитку менеджерів у Китаї: від університетської підготовки до безперервного самовдосконалення

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***Анотація:** У XXI столітті глобалізація та цифрова трансформація економіки докорінно змінили вимоги до управлінських кадрів. Менеджери перестали бути адміністраторами процесів і стали стратегічними лідерами, здатними інтегрувати інновації, працювати з великими масивами даних та забезпечувати конкурентоспроможність організацій. Професійний розвиток*

управлінців нині розглядається як стратегічний ресурс, що формує людський капітал і визначає сталий розвиток економіки. Метою статті є аналіз моделей професійного розвитку менеджерів у Китаї та простеження їхньої еволюції від університетської підготовки до концепції *lifelong learning*. У роботі розглянуто ключові процеси трансформації управлінської освіти: масифікацію та інтернаціоналізацію університетської підготовки. Масове залучення студентів створило широку базу для розвитку людського капіталу, а інтеграція міжнародних стандартів сприяла формуванню глобально орієнтованих менеджерів. Визначено гібридність освітніх моделей, що поєднують західні інновації з конфуціанськими цінностями, забезпечуючи конкурентоспроможність випускників на світовому ринку. Особлива увага приділена ролі викладача як морального наставника та впливу конфуціанської етики на сучасні програми MBA й корпоративну культуру компаній. Цифровізація освіти стала ключовим чинником професійного розвитку менеджерів. Національна платформа *Smart Education of China* інтегрує цифрові технології у навчальний процес, створюючи екосистему для формування компетенцій. Корпоративні університети та бізнес-школи пропонують практичні програми з цифрової трансформації, управління інноваціями та автоматизації бізнес-процесів. *Lifelong learning* у Китаї виступає стратегічною основою професійного розвитку, адже поєднує академічну освіту, корпоративні тренінги та цифрові курси, формуючи культуру безперервного навчання. Китайський досвід має значний потенціал для міжнародної адаптації. Його системність і багаторівневість дозволяють поєднувати фундаментальні знання, прикладні навички та *lifelong learning* в єдину освітню екосистему. Для міжнародної практики управлінської освіти цей досвід відкриває можливості масштабної цифровізації, розвитку корпоративних університетів та формування глобальної культури безперервного навчання. Водночас адаптація китайських моделей потребує

врахування національних особливостей: рівня розвитку цифрової інфраструктури, ресурсів малого й середнього бізнесу, культурних традицій у сфері освіти. Лише за умови гнучкого підходу цей досвід може бути ефективно інтегрований у міжнародну практику, створюючи нові моделі професійного розвитку, що відповідають викликам глобалізованого світу.

***Ключові слова:** професійний розвиток менеджерів, організаційно–педагогічні засади, управлінська компетентність, освітнє середовище університету, цифровізація освіти, lifelong learning, міжнародна адаптація*

Models of Managerial Professional Development in China: from University Training to Lifelong Self-Improvement

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Abstract: *In the 21st century, globalization and digital transformation have fundamentally reshaped the requirements for managerial staff. Managers ceased to be mere administrators of processes and became strategic leaders capable of integrating innovations, working with large datasets, and ensuring organizational competitiveness. Managerial professional development is now regarded as a strategic resource that builds human capital and determines sustainable economic growth. The purpose of the article is to analyze models of managerial professional development in China and to trace their evolution from university training to the concept of lifelong learning. The study aims to identify the strengths and weaknesses of Chinese practices, examine their hybrid nature, and assess their potential for international adaptation. The paper explores key processes of managerial education transformation: large-scale scope and internationalization of university training. The expansion of student enrollment created a broad base for human capital development, while the integration of international standards contributed to the formation of globally oriented managers. The hybrid nature of educational models, combining Western innovations with Confucian values, ensures the competitiveness of graduates in the global market. Particular attention is paid to the role of the teacher as a moral mentor and the influence of Confucian ethics on modern MBA programs and corporate culture. Digitalization of education has become a crucial factor in managerial professional development. The national platform Smart Education of China integrates digital technologies into the learning process, creating an ecosystem for competence formation. Corporate universities and business schools offer practical programs in digital transformation, innovation management, and business process automation. Lifelong learning in China serves as a strategic foundation for professional development, combining academic education, corporate training, and digital courses to foster the culture of continuous learning. Chinese experience has significant potential for international adaptation. Its systemic and multi-level approach allows the integration of fundamental knowledge, applied skills,*

and lifelong learning into a single educational ecosystem. For international managerial education, this experience opens opportunities for large scale digitalization, the development of corporate universities, and the establishment of a global culture of continuous learning. At the same time, adaptation of Chinese models requires consideration of national specificities: the level of digital infrastructure, resources of small and medium-sized businesses, and cultural traditions in education. This experience can be effectively integrated into international practice only with a flexible approach, creating new models of professional development that meet the challenges of a globalized world.

Keywords: *managerial professional development, organizational and pedagogical foundations, managerial competence, university educational environment, digitalization of education, lifelong learning, international adaptation.*

General problem statement and its connection with important scientific and practical tasks. In the 21st century, globalization and the digital transformation of the economy have fundamentally changed the requirements for managerial personnel. Managers are no longer merely administrators of processes – they have become strategic leaders capable of adapting to rapid changes, integrating innovations, and ensuring organizational competitiveness in the global market. Today, highly qualified managers determine the success of companies across diverse sectors, from manufacturing to high technology, and from financial services to education. Therefore, managerial professional development is regarded as a strategic resource that builds human capital and ensures sustainable economic growth.

It should be noted that over the past three decades, China has transformed into one of the world's leading economies, and this success is largely explained by its effective system of managerial training. On the one hand, universities and business schools provide fundamental education, integrating international standards and

adapting them to the local context. On the other hand, major corporations such as Huawei, Alibaba, and Tencent have established their own corporate universities and personnel development programs, which combine mentoring, practical training, and digital platforms. This enables managers to continuously update their knowledge and develop competencies necessary for operating in a globalized market environment.

Analysis of Recent Research and Publications has shown that some aspects of this problem are presented in scientific literature. Thus, studies by Qiu and Sun [1] demonstrate the evolution of the internationalization of Chinese higher education; however, they scarcely address the specifics of managerial professional training. Wang [2] analyzes the impact of globalization on education, but this focus is primarily on social inequality rather than managerial competencies. Wei Xiaolong, Ming Yufeng, Jun Jie, and Jia Hao [3] explore the transformation of the system between Confucian traditions and modernization, yet they leave open the question of the practical impact of these changes on managerial education. Ji Ying and Liz Jackson [4] examine the moral role of teachers, which is important for educational culture, but they do not explain how these aspects are integrated into managerial training. Beekun et al. [5] and Wei He [6] highlight the influence of Confucian values on business ethics and management. In the field of digitalization, Wang, Shi, and Chang [7] outline trends and challenges, though their analysis concerns education in general without detailing managerial competencies. Han and colleagues [8] investigate corporate universities as instruments of lifelong learning, but they do not reveal how these institutions affect managers' career trajectories. Fang, Zheng, and Xia [9] describe the modernization of lifelong learning, yet they overlook the issue of international adaptation of Chinese experience.

Thus, **the main gaps in the literature** lie in the insufficient analysis of the specifics of managerial professional development, the lack of research on the integration of digital tools into managerial training, limited attention to the career

implications of lifelong learning, and the absence of comparative studies on the application of Chinese experience in international managerial education.

The purpose of this article is to provide a comprehensive analysis of models of managerial professional development in China and to trace their evolution from university training to the concept of lifelong learning.

To achieve this, it is considered necessary to address the following **tasks**:

1. outline the general context and current trends in the development of managerial education under conditions of globalization, focusing on the role of highly qualified managers in ensuring the competitiveness of the economy and organizations.
2. identify the strengths and problematic aspects of Chinese models of managerial professional development, tracing their evolution from university training to corporate programs and the concept of lifelong learning.
3. determine the potential of Chinese experience for international managerial education practice, highlighting the possibilities of its adaptation and application in other countries.

Findings. In today's world, globalization and the digital transformation of the economy are radically reshaping approaches to management education, setting new requirements for the professional training of managers. Highly qualified executives are becoming a key resource for the competitiveness of both individual companies and national economies, as they are capable of integrating innovations, adapting to rapid changes, and ensuring the strategic development of organizations. In this context, China demonstrates a unique example of the transformation of the management education system, which combines university training, corporate programs, and the concept of lifelong learning.

Based on the analysis of scholarly literature, the following contemporary trends can be identified:

- Large-scale scope and internationalization of education;

- Hybridization of educational models;
- Digitalization of learning;
- Lifelong learning.

The analysis of academic sources shows that one of the key processes is the *large-scale scope of education* – the rapid growth in the number of students obtaining higher education. Whereas in the 1980s Chinese universities were accessible only to a limited elite, by the early 2000s the state had implemented large-scale programs to expand access, enabling millions of young people to pursue university studies. This not only increased quantitative indicators but also created a new quality of the educational environment, where competition among students and institutions stimulated the raising of academic standards. Large-scale scope has become an important factor in the formation of human capital, which underpins the competitiveness of the economy [1, p. 115].

At the same time, the process of *internationalization of education* unfolded, meaning the active integration of Chinese universities into the global educational space. Institutions of higher learning in China began collaborating with leading universities worldwide, launching joint programs, and attracting foreign faculty and students. This facilitated the dissemination of international standards of management education, including MBA programs, the case method, and corporate learning practices. At the same time, Chinese universities adapted these models to the local context, combining Western innovations with traditional cultural values such as the Confucian ethic of service to society.

Internationalization also manifested itself in the growing mobility of students: tens of thousands of Chinese citizens study abroad each year, while foreign students increasingly choose China as a destination for higher education. This creates a two-way exchange of knowledge and cultural practices, shaping globally oriented managers capable of working in multicultural environments [2, p. 101].

Thus, the large-scale scope and internationalization of education in China have become interconnected processes that have ensured the development of new models of managerial training. The broad involvement of students created a solid foundation for the growth of human capital, while international cooperation endowed this capital with global quality. As a result, China has acquired a system of management education that combines quantitative expansion with qualitative integration into the global educational space.

It can be stated that China's educational system today stands at the intersection of two powerful traditions – global Western approaches and deeply rooted Confucian values. On the one hand, Chinese universities and business schools actively integrate international standards, such as MBA programs, the Harvard Business School case method, and accreditation practices based on Western models. This enables students to receive an education that meets the demands of the global labor market and ensures the international competitiveness of graduates. On the other hand, the Chinese educational tradition continues to rely on Confucian philosophy, which emphasizes the cultivation of moral leaders, civic service, and harmony between personal interests and the public good. Chinese universities do not simply replicate Western methodologies but adapt them to their own cultural context. MBA programs in China often include modules on ethics, public service, and social responsibility, reflecting the Confucian idea of serving society [3].

The role of the teacher in China has traditionally been viewed as that of a moral mentor. Even in modern business schools, instructors not only transmit knowledge but also shape students' value orientations. This distinguishes the Chinese model from the Western one, where the emphasis is placed on individual autonomy and critical thinking [4, p. 455].

At the same time, Confucian values are actively integrated into the sphere of business education. Scholars highlight that Confucian principles of harmony, justice, and collective responsibility influence MBA curricula and shape a distinctive

business-ethical culture. This allows Chinese graduates to combine global managerial skills with local cultural norms [5].

For example, Wei He demonstrates that Confucian philosophy continues to define management practices in Chinese internet companies, particularly Alibaba. The author emphasizes that principles such as benevolence (Ren), harmony (Li), collectivism, and long-term thinking (Zhi) shape leadership style, corporate culture, and employee relations. These values foster trust, strengthen team cohesion, and ensure a balance between individual and collective interests [6].

Importantly, these values are not perceived as archaic but are adapted to the conditions of the digital economy. In Alibaba's practice, they manifest in the pursuit of harmonious development, social responsibility, and ethical regulation of business. Thus, the Confucian tradition becomes not only a cultural legacy but also a tool of strategic management that ensures the competitiveness of Chinese companies in the global market [6; 8].

Consequently, the Chinese educational model is not a simple mixture of Western and traditional approaches. It creates a new quality—a system that simultaneously prepares students for global competition and shapes them as moral leaders capable of serving the state and society. This hybridity can be regarded as China's strategic advantage in shaping the educational space of the 21 century.

Digitalization of education in China has become a key factor in shaping a new model of managerial professional development. Whereas university training previously focused on classical disciplines such as economics, production organization, and personnel management, today it integrates digital technologies that transform the very nature of managerial activity. The new generation of managers must not only possess knowledge but also be able to work with large datasets, apply artificial intelligence in decision-making, and organize business processes in a digital environment [7].

At the university level, an important role is played by the Smart Education of China (SEC) – a national educational platform that unites hundreds of thousands of institutions and millions of users. It creates a unified digital ecosystem where management students can work with interactive cases, analyze data, and model managerial decisions. This enables the combination of theoretical training with practical skills of immediate applicability. According to the Ministry of Education of the PRC, as of 2023 more than 519,000 institutions were connected to SEC, encompassing nearly 19 million teachers and 293 million students [10; 11]. Such scale demonstrates the systemic nature of the state's approach to educational digitalization.

The concept of lifelong learning has become a strategic necessity for the contemporary Chinese model. Its strength lies in scale and state support. China actively develops adult universities, online courses, and professional development programs, enabling managers to continuously update their competencies and remain competitive. Lifelong learning is integrated into national strategies for educational modernization, combining political, technological, and cultural resources. Research by Fang et al. shows that the Chinese model of lifelong learning has significant potential, as it aims to create a system in which learning becomes an integral part of professional life. A problematic aspect, however, is managerial overload: the constant need to study may lead to stress and reduced motivation. Moreover, the quality of online courses does not always meet high standards, which diminishes the effectiveness of lifelong learning [9; 12].

Tracing the evolution of Chinese models of managerial professional development reveals several key trends. First, the transition from university training to corporate programs marked a shift from theoretical foundations to practical orientation. Second, the move from corporate programs to lifelong learning expanded opportunities for all categories of managers. Third, the strengths of the model include scale, digitalization, practicality, and state support. At the same time, problematic

aspects remain: the gap between theory and practice, inequality of access, managerial overload, and uneven course quality.

Overall, the Chinese model of managerial professional development demonstrates systemic and strategic coherence, combining university education, corporate programs, and lifelong learning into a unified system. It creates conditions for cultivating a new generation of managers—flexible, innovative, and capable of operating in the global digital environment. To enhance the effectiveness of this model, however, university curricula must be adapted to business needs, small and medium enterprises must be supported in corporate training, and the quality of lifelong learning programs must be improved. The combination of digitalization, practical orientation, and a culture of continuous learning makes the Chinese model unique, while simultaneously presenting new challenges that will shape its future.

Conclusions. China's experience in managerial professional development demonstrates significant potential for adaptation in other countries. Its primary value lies in systemic and multi-level integration: from university training with embedded digital technologies, through corporate programs with strong practical orientation, to state-supported lifelong learning. This model illustrates how fundamental knowledge, applied skills, and a culture of continuous education can be combined into a coherent educational ecosystem. For international practice in management education, the Chinese case offers several opportunities. Firstly, universities elsewhere may adopt large-scale digitalization of the learning process, using national platforms to build digital competencies among future managers. Secondly, corporate universities and business schools can adapt China's model of practice-oriented training, which responds quickly to market needs and integrates innovative technologies into business processes. Thirdly, the concept of lifelong learning may serve as a foundation for establishing a global culture of continuous education, enabling managers to update knowledge and remain competitive in the digital economy.

Список використаних джерел (ДСТУ 8302:2015)

Список використаних джерел подається за порядком згадування в тексті статті, здійснюється відповідно до Національного стандарту України ДСТУ 8302:2015. Бібліографічне посилання. Загальні положення та правила складання. <http://lib.pnu.edu.ua/files/dstu-8302-2015.pdf>

Забороняється цитування в тексті та внесення до бібліографічних списків тих джерел, які опубліковані російською мовою в будь-якій країні, а також джерел іншими мовами, якщо вони опубліковані на території росії та білорусі.

У тексті, номер джерела зі списку вказується в квадратних дужках, разом із зазначенням номера сторінки, наприклад: [1, с. 12] або [1, р. 12], якщо посилання англomовне. Використання посилань на підручники, науково-популярну літературу та власні публікації допускається лише у випадках нагальної потреби.

Якщо в огляді літератури або в подальшому тексті вказано прізвище вченого, його публікація повинна з'явитися у списку літератури після статті.

У списку літератури має бути не менше ніж 15 наукових джерел, до яких належать: наукові статті, збірники наукових статей, монографії, тощо. Статті з вебресурсів, сайти, нормативно-правові документи тощо не вважають науковими джерелами. Вікіпедія не є авторитетним джерелом, її використання в списку літератури заборонено.

У списку літератури не можна згадувати більше двох робіт одного автора (винятком є випадки, коли в статті проводять аналіз творчості якогось діяча).

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